

How to Make Your Data FAIR

Applying the [FAIR Principles](#) allows for the best reuse of your research data. This will make your research more transparent, reproducible, and citable. It will also help you meet publisher and funder requirements and open up opportunities for collaboration. So how can you make your data FAIR?

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